

Organizational Communication Ethics in Supporting Service Quality in Government

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Abstract:- The purpose of the author of this study is to investigate the ethics of organizational communication to support service quality in the government of Sinjai Regency. This research uses a combination of quantitative and qualitative techniques (mixed method), which are used alternately with the interactive triangle method, which aims to provide a clear picture and description of the existing problems related to communication ethics. of the entire organization. supporting service quality in Sinjai Regency Government. Questionnaires, interviews and documentation are used as data collection methods with purposive sampling, where the choice of informants is deliberately chosen based on the criteria included in the research objectives. The subjects of this study were the Regional Secretary, Echelon II and Echelon III and Sinjai Regency Community. Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that the ethics of organizational communication supporting service quality has been well implemented in the board of Sinjai Regency as a whole. The principle of friendship in information transmission and communication is very good. It has also been well applied to other principles such as the principle of justice. As for the principle of freedom as a whole, it is well done because the government of Sinjai Regency gives every community the freedom to exercise their right to express their opinion. The general principle of truth was also applied well because the government of Sinjai Regency mediates the disclosure of information, always broadcasting true information following the principles of truth.

Keywords: *Organizational Communication Ethics, Service Quality.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Communication in English is communication and in Latin comes from the word *communicatio* which means sharing or belonging together, and comes from the word *communis* which means the same. The point is the same meaning. Carl I. Hovland defines communication as follows: "The process by which an individual (the communicator) transmits stimuli (usually verbal symbols) to modify the behavior of other individuals (communicants)," (The process by which a person (communicator) conveys stimuli (usually symbols of language) to change the behavior of others (communicants). (Effendy, 2011).

Communication cannot be separated from ethics. Ethics in communication has an important role in making a communication well established. Ethics is the application of the process and theory of moral philosophy to real situations. Ethics centers on the basic principles and concepts that humans in their thinking and actions are based on values. (Apdillah, dkk, 2022).

The application of communication ethics is also usually applied in an agency or organization and others. This is related to organizational behavior in carrying out the communication process. Organizational behavior is concerned with how people act and react in all types of organizations. In organizational life, people are employed, educated and trained, informed, protected and developed. In other words, organizational behavior is how people behave in an organization. Organization is a social unit that is mutually consciously coordinated, consisting of 2 (two) or more people who function on a relatively continuous basis to achieve goals (Robbins and Judge, 2011), together or a series of goals. It is also said that an organization is a consciously coordinated system of activities of 2 or more people (Keitner and Kinicki, 2009).

Sinjai Regency is supported by 17 human resources consisting of 13 civil servants and 4 non-civil servants as shown in the following table:

Table 1: Number of Human Resources of the Regional Secretariat of Sinjai Regency

1.	Number of civil servants	250
2.	Number of Non-civil servants	150
	Total	400
3.	Civil Servants by Gender	
	-Male	180
	-Women	220
4.	Civil Servants by Class	
	-Group II	175
	-Group III	140
	-Class IV	85
5.	Civil Servants by Education	
	-High school graduate	163
	-Diploma III	32
	-S1	180
	-S2	25

Source: Regional Secretariat of Sinjai Regency, 2023

The level of education is a condition of the level of education possessed by a person through formal education used by the government and authorized by the education department. The following are Sinjai Regency employees when viewed or detailed based on the level of high school education as many as 163 people, Diploma as many as 32 people, S1 as many as 180 people and S2 as many as 25 people. In order for the agency's operations to run smoothly, it is necessary to have harmonious communication both between employees and with the leadership. With harmonious communication both vertically and horizontally, it is expected to be able to improve employee work and ultimately have an impact on employee work productivity and provide good service to the community.

Providing services is a form of respect for the community as service recipients. Communication ethics need to be considered so that there is no prejudice that can have a negative impact on other employees. Every employee should not issue words that are less pleasing to the ear that can make other people's feelings become offended in providing services. Thus communication ethics plays an important role in conducting work relations in government agencies, especially at the Sinjai Regency Office.

Some studies that support the relationship of organizational communication ethics to service quality include this study to get participants' perspectives on the effect of administrative ethics on service quality where this study combines quantitative and associative approaches by (Latif, 2023). Then this study aims to determine the ethics of the apparatus on service quality at the Sidenreng Rappang Regency National Land Agency office. This type of research is quantitative associative where this research uses two types of variables, namely variable X (apparatus ethics) and variable Y (service quality) by (Pujiawati and Tajuddin, 2023). And this study aims to determine the effect of Ethics and Quality of Service of Health Workers on Patient Satisfaction at Dr. Soepraoen Hospital Malang where the research method used is descriptive analytical research with a cross sectional study design by (Efendi, et al, 2021).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Communication Ethics*

Communication ethics is often used to look at the good or bad ways of communicating in people's lives. This ethic covers the field of verbal and nonverbal communication. In verbal communication, the ethics in question is the use of language, both orally and in writing. Meanwhile, nonverbal communication ethics include how to dress, how to behave, and so on.

According to Abdul Samad Arief, et.,al (2021) in the book *Basics of Business Communication*, ethics are principles for regulating behavior in society. Meanwhile, communication is a relationship of interaction between people, in the form of sending and receiving messages. So communication ethics can be interpreted as principles that regulate interaction relationships between people. Communication ethics can also be defined as norms, values, and behaviors in establishing communication. Launching from the Encyclopedia website, communication ethics is an ethical responsibility in communicating, whether done directly or through communication technology, such as gadgets and social media. Historically, communication ethics has its roots in journalism ethics. Due to the proliferation of communication media during the last half of the 20th century, the term media ethics is sometimes used as a synonym for communication ethics (Vanya Karunia Mulia Putri, 2021: 2). The use of ethics in communication aims to convey information appropriately, build good relationships, as a form of courtesy, and part of mutual respect and appreciation for others.

Communication ethics includes the art of speaking or politeness in speaking to be understood by the public, speech ethics can show the moral quality of a person because how to convey ideas, ideas through language will reveal the level of degree and dignity and the weight of one's moral ethics, so we often hear that language shows who he is, who he is, and even shows the identity of his nation. (Purwadi, 2020).

B. Service Quality

According to Fandy Tjiptono (2017: 180) defines service quality or service quality as a measure of how good the level of service provided is able to match customer expectations. Meanwhile, according to Jeon and Jeong (2017) states that service quality is a comparison between the perceived service (perception) of customers and the quality of service expected by customers.

According to Leon G Schiffman, et.,al (2015) states that it is more difficult for consumers to evaluate the quality of service than the quality of products. This is true because of certain distinctive characteristics of services: they are intangible, they are variable, they are perishable, and they are simultaneously produced and consumed. Which means that it is more difficult for consumers to evaluate service quality than product quality. This is true because of the special characteristics of certain services: they are intangible, they are variable, they are perishable because they have to maintain a reputation, and they are simultaneously produced and consumed.

According to Kotler in Etta Mamang Sangadji (2013: 99) states that service or service quality is a dynamic condition related to products, services, people, processes, and environments that meet or exceed expectations. Meanwhile, according to Atep Adya Brata (2003: 36) states that talking about service quality, the size is not only determined by the serving party but is more determined by the party being served, because they are the ones who enjoy the service so that they can measure service quality based on their expectations in meeting their satisfaction.

5 Service Quality Perspectives According to Garvin in Fandy Tjiptono (2017: 129) states that there are at least five quality perspectives currently developing: transcendental approach, product-based approach, user-based approach, manufacturing-based approach, and value-based approach.

- **Transcendental Approach** In this perspective, quality is seen as innate excellence, which is something that can be intuitively understood, but almost impossible to communicate, such as beauty or love. This perspective asserts that people can only learn to understand quality through experience gained from repeated exposure. For example, products or services of music, drama, painting, dance and visual arts.
- **Product based approach** This perspective assumes that quality is an objective characteristic, component or attribute that can be quantified and measured. For example, laptop products that have different specifications of micro processors, memory capacity, RAM, additional features (Wifi, web cam), price, size and weight.
- **User-based approach** This perspective is based on the idea that quality depends on the person who judges it (eyes of the beholder), so that the product that best satisfies one's preferences (maximum satisfaction) is the highest quality product. This subjective and demand-oriented perspective also states that each customer has their own needs and desires that are different from one another, so quality for a person is the same as the maximum satisfaction he feels. For example, sweet, salty, spicy, and coconut milk dishes or foods have their own fans.
- **Manufacturing based approach** This perspective is supply-based and focuses more on engineering and manufacturing practices, and defines quality as conformance to requirements.
- **Value-based approach** This perspective views quality from the aspects of value and price. By considering the trade off between performance and price, quality is defined as affordable excellence, namely the best level of performance or commensurate with the price paid. Quality in this perspective is relative, so the highest quality product is not necessarily the most valuable product. For example, a quality economy car is different from a quality luxury car.

Fig. 1: Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at the Regional Government of Sinjai Regency, South Sulawesi Province. This location was chosen because the Sinjai District Government has services that need to be slightly improved so that services to the community can run well. Determination of informants through questionnaire, interview and documentation methods carried out by purposive sampling where the selection of informants is selected deliberately based on the criteria contained in the research objectives. The research object in this study is the Regional Secretary, Echelons II and III and the people of Sinjai Regency. The data analysis technique used in this research is a combination of quantitative and qualitative techniques (mixed method) used alternately, using an interactive analysis model with the triangulation method developed by Miles and Huberman (Moleong, 2007). The formula used in data analysis (mixed method) is as follows:

$$P = f \times 100\% N$$

Description :

P = Percentage

F = Frequency obtained from respondents' answers

N = Number of Respondents

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organizational communication ethics in supporting service quality at the Sinjai Regency Government Office.

A. The Principle of Kindness

The principle of kindness is the basis for delivering information about all government actions in providing services to the community which are intended to balance things that benefit the community when getting services. The research was conducted by distributing questionnaires to 27 people, then the data was processed in tabular form and then analyzed as follows:

Table 2: The Principle of Employee Kindness in Supporting Quality Licensing Service

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	12	44%
Good	10	37%
Less Good	5	19%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that most people assess the principle of attention of supporting officials to the quality of licensing services is very good. This can be clearly seen from community input, 44% answered very well, 10% answered

well and 5% answered less and none of the community answered less well. Thus, it can be concluded that most of the community assessed that the principle of kind staff supporting the quality of licensing services is very good.

Table 3: The Principle of Kindness of Employees in Supporting the Quality of General Service

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	6	22%
Good	12	45%
Less Good	7	26%
Not good	2	7%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee kindness in supporting the quality of public services is good, this can be seen from the community's answer of 22% who answered very well, some answered well by 45%, and those who answered less well by

26%, and 2% of people who answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle of employee kindness in supporting the quality of public services to be good.

Table 4: Principles of Employee Kindness in Supporting Service Quality PBB

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	18	67%
Good	8	29%
Less Good	1	4%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee kindness in supporting the quality of population administration services is good, this can be seen from the public's answer of 15% who answered very well,

some answered well by 67%, and those who answered less well by 11%, and 7% of people who answered not well.

67%, and those who answered less well were 11%, and 7% of people who answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle

of employee kindness in supporting the quality of population administration services to be good.

Table 5: The Principle of Kindness of Employees in Supporting the Quality of Population Administration Services Population Administration

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	4	15%
Good	18	67%
Less Good	3	11%
Not good	2	7%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee kindness in supporting the quality of PBB services is very good, this can be seen from the community's answers of 67% who answered very well, some answered well by 29%, and those who answered less well by 4%, and no community answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the

principle of employee kindness in supporting the quality of population administration services to be very good.

Based on the results of observations through document data, it is known that the application of the principle of kindness in supporting the quality of service at the Sinjai Regency Government Office has been carried out by employees at the Sinjai Regency Government Office can be seen in the following table:

Table 6: Application of the Principle of Kindness in Service

No	Type of Service	Principle of Kindness
1	Licensing Service	Very good
2	General Services	Good
3	Population Administration Services	Good
4	PBB Service	Very good

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

The principle of kindness in building communication ethics when providing services to the community is through the delivery of information that is clear and easily understood by the community, this was conveyed by the Regional Secretary of Sinjai Regency, through the following interview results:

"The principles of kindness that we apply as a form of ethics in communication to support service quality are by conveying information that is clear and easy to understand or understand by the community such as delivery of service procedures or service requirements." (Interview on July 31, 2023).

Furthermore, from the results of an interview with the Head of the General Service Section through an interview as follows:

B. Justice

"In my opinion, effective communication between the parties must be two-way communication (reciprocal). This requires the cooperation of all parties (employees and leaders) to achieve organizational goals. Effective communication strategies have been implemented in the district office so that the intended goals can be achieved" (Interview on July 20, 2023).

From the results of the analysis above, it shows that in providing services to the community, Sinjai Regency Government employees have applied the principle of kindness in public communication ethics by conveying information that is clear and easily understood by the public, besides that the application of effective communication is also carried out between employees and leaders through two-way communication to achieve organizational goals.

Table 7: The Principle of Employee Fairness in Supporting the Quality of Licensing Service

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	9	33%
Good	13	48%
Less Good	5	19%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee justice in supporting the quality of licensing services is good, this can be seen from the community's answers of 33% who answered very well, 48% who answered well, and 19% who answered less well, and

there were no people who answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle of employee justice in supporting the quality of licensing services to be good.

Table 8: The Principle of Employee Fairness in Supporting the Quality of General Service

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	4	15%
Good	15	55%
Less Good	8	30%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee justice in supporting the quality of public services is good, this can be seen from the public's answer of 15% who answered very well, some answered well by 55%, and those who answered less well by 30%, and

there were no people who answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle of employee justice in supporting the quality of public services to be good.

Table 9: Principles of Employee Fairness in Supporting Service Quality Population Administration

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	11	41%
Good	15	55%
Less Good	1	4%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee justice in supporting the quality of population administration services is good, this can be seen from the community's answers of 41% who answered very well, 55% who answered well, and 4% who answered less

well, and no community who answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle of employee justice in supporting the quality of population administration services to be good.

Table 10: The Principle of Fairness of Employees in Supporting the Quality of Service PBB

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	10	37%
Good	12	44%
Less Good	5	19%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of fairness of employees in supporting the quality of PBB services is very good, this can be seen from the answers of the community of 37% who answered very well, some answered well by 44%, and those who answered less well by 19%, and there were no people who answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people

consider the principle of employee justice in supporting the quality of population administration services to be good.

Based on the results of observations through document data, it is known that the application of the principle of fairness in supporting the quality of services at the Sinjai Regency Government Office has been carried out by employees at the Sinjai Regency Government Office can be seen in the following table:

Table 11: Application of the Principle of Fairness in Service

No	Type of Service	Principle of Justice
1	Licensing Service	Good
2	General Services	Good
3	Population Administration Services	Good
4	PBB Service	Good

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

From the results of the analysis above, it shows that in providing services to the community, Sinjai Regency Government employees have applied the principle of justice in communication by providing equal treatment to all levels of society without discriminating between one community and another. In the sense that all people have the right to obtain information about the services provided by employees in the Sinjai Regency Government.

The application of the principle of justice in conveying public information to the public has gone well. All people can easily access information that has been provided by the Regency government either directly or indirectly.

C. Principle of Freedom

The principle of freedom is the basis for being free to make policies and take actions in accordance with the duties and functions of the government. The application of this

principle does not mean that the government can act arbitrarily, but rather shows that attitudes or actions must be accounted for. This means that even though government intervention in the lives of citizens is an action that must be taken by the government to overcome problems that exist in the midst of society, the government must dare to be responsible for these actions.

To obtain data on the principle of freedom in providing services to the community, the author made a questionnaire consisting of 4 questions that must be answered by the public which contains the principle of freedom applied by employees in the Office of the Regional Secretary of Sinjai Regency. The research was conducted by distributing questionnaires to 27 people, then the data was processed in tabular form and then analyzed as follows:

Table 12: The Principle of Employee Freedom in Supporting the Quality of Licensing Services Licensing Service

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	12	44%
Good	10	37%
Less Good	5	19%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee freedom in supporting the quality of licensing services is very good, this can be seen from the community's answer of 44% who answered very well, some answered well by 10%, and those who answered less were

5%, and there were no people who answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle of employee freedom in supporting the quality of licensing services to be very good.

Table 13: The Principle of Employee Freedom in Supporting the Quality of Public Services General Service

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	18	67%
Good	8	29%
Less Good	1	4%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee freedom in supporting the quality of public services is very good, this can be seen from the community's answers of 67% who answered very well, some answered well by 29%, and those who answered less

well by 4%, and no community answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle of employee kindness in supporting the quality of public services to be very good.

Table 14: The Principle of Employee Freedom in Supporting the Quality of Population Administration Services Population Administration Services

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	6	22%
Good	12	45%
Less Good	7	26%
Not good	2	7%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee freedom in supporting the quality of population administration services is good, this can be seen

from the community's answer of 22% who answered very well, some answered well by 45%, and those who answered less well by 26%, and 2% of people who answered not well.

Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle of employee freedom in supporting

the quality of population administration services to be good.

Table 15: The Principle of Employee Freedom in Supporting the Quality of PBB Services

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	4	15%
Good	18	67%
Less Good	3	11%
Not good	2	7%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee freedom in supporting the quality of PBB services is good, this can be seen from the public's answer of 15% who answered very well, some answered well by 67%, and those who answered less well by 11%, and 7% of people who answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle

of employee freedom in supporting the quality of PBB services to be good.

Based on the results of observations through document data, it is known that the application of the principle of freedom in supporting the quality of services at the Sinjai Regency Government Office has been carried out by employees at the Sinjai Regency Government Office can be seen in the following table:

Table 16: Application of the Principle of Freedom in Service

No	Type of Service	Principle of Justice
1	Licensing Service	Very good
2	General Services	Very good
3	Population Administration Services	Good
4	PBB Service	Good

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

From the results of the analysis above, it shows that in providing services to the community, Sinjai Regency Government employees have applied the principle of freedom in communication by providing the widest possible opportunity and freedom to the public to express opinions. In the sense that all people have the right to express their opinions in a good and ethical manner.

Based on the results of observations through document data at the Sinjai Regency Government Office, the application of the principle of freedom in expressing opinions and in the form of complaints submitted to Sinjai Regency Government employees. The following are several types of complaints that have been submitted directly by the community:

Table 17: Application of the Principle of Freedom in Service

No	Type of Complaint
1	Tree Felling
2	Damage to Irrigation Construction
3	Damage to Road Construction
4	Land Acquisition Compensation
5	Wild Racing
6	Wild Livestock

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

Based on the table above, it can be explained that one form of the principle of freedom given by the Sinjai Regency government in communication is in terms of submitting complaints related to existing problems. Furthermore, from various types of complaints, they received good responses and responses from the District Government.

Furthermore, from the results of an interview by the Head of General and Personnel Subdivision Lamain through an interview as follows:

"The principle of freedom of communication is the right of every person so that we as public servants certainly uphold this right by providing freedom for every community to express opinions" (Interview on July 20, 2023).

Furthermore, from the results of an interview with one of the citizens in the Sinjai Regency Government, Mr. Alimuddin explained as follows:

"Regarding freedom of communication, I think everyone is free to speak as long as it is in a good and polite way. And at the Sub-District Office itself I think every community can speak, it's just that what is lacking is usually the response from employees" (Interview on July 20, 2023).

From the results of the interview above, it can be explained that regarding freedom of communication, every community is free to express their opinions in a good and correct way. This was also expressed by Mrs. Ramlah who said that:

"If the problem of freedom in communication I think it is good, is the opportunity given to the community to speak or express opinions" (Interview on July 20, 2023).

Furthermore, from the results of an interview with Mrs. Nurliah said that:

"Yes, all people are given freedom of communication. I as the community every time I go to the Sub-District Office, I am always given the opportunity to speak" (Interview on July 18, 2023).

Based on the results and descriptions above, it can be concluded that the indicators of the principle of freedom applied in the Office of the Regional Secretary of the Regency of Sinjai as a form of organizational communication ethics in supporting service quality as a whole have been carried out well because the Government of Sinjai Regency Government provides freedom for every community to exercise their rights in expressing opinions.

D. The truth principle

The principle of truth is the basis for government behavior to provide public information in accordance with actual data and facts. The application of this principle means that the government must provide information clearly and can be proven by the government so that the truth can be believed by the public.

To obtain data on the principle of truth in providing services to the public, the author made a questionnaire consisting of 4 questions that must be answered by the public which contains the principle of truth applied by employees in the Office of the Regional Secretary of Sinjai Regency. The research was conducted by distributing questionnaires to 27 people, then the data was processed in tabular form and then analyzed as follows:

Table 18: The Principle of Employee Truth in Supporting the Quality of Licensing Services Licensing Service

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	13	59%
Good	9	41%
Less Good	5	0%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee truthfulness in supporting the quality of licensing services is good, this can be seen from the community's answers of 59% who answered very well,

some answered well by 41%, and no one answered less well and not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle of employee truthfulness in supporting the quality of licensing services to be very good.

Table 19: The Principle of Employee Correctness in Supporting the Quality of Public Services General Service

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	13	48%
Good	9	33%
Less Good	5	19%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee truthfulness in supporting the quality of public services is very good, this can be seen from the public's answer of 48% who answered very well, some answered well by 33%, and those who answered less well by

19%, and no people answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle of employee truthfulness in supporting the quality of public services to be good.

Table 20: The Principle of Employee Correctness in Supporting the Quality of Population Administration Services

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	11	41%
Good	15	55%
Less Good	1	4%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee truthfulness in supporting the quality of population administration services is good, this can be seen from the community's answer of 41% who answered very well, some answered well by 55%, and those who answered less well by 4%, and there were no people who answered not well.

55%, and those who answered less well were 4%, and there were no people who answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people consider the principle of employee truthfulness in supporting the quality of population administration services to be good.

Table 21: The Principle of Employee Correctness in Supporting the Quality of Service PBB

Alternative Answer	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Very good	12	45%
Good	9	33%
Less Good	6	22%
Not good	0	0%
Total	27	100

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

It can be seen that the majority of people say that the principle of employee truthfulness in supporting the quality of PBB services is very good, this can be seen from the community's answer of 45% who answered very well, some answered well by 33%, and those who answered less well by 22%, and there were no people who answered not well. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of people

consider the principle of employee truth in supporting the quality of PBB services to be very good.

Based on the results of observations through document data, it is known that the application of the principle of truth in supporting the quality of services at the Sinjai Regency Government Office has been carried out by employees at the Sinjai Regency Government Office can be seen in the following table:

Table 22: Application of the Principle of Truth in Service

No	Type of Service	Principle of Truth
1	Licensing Service	Good
2	General Services	Good
3	Population Administration Services	Good
4	PBB Service	Good

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

The principle of truth applied as a form of organizational communication ethics in supporting service quality is through openness in the delivery of information in accordance with the actual situation conveyed by the Regional Secretary of Sinjai Regency, Andi Baso Mangunrawa SE through the following interview results:

"The principles of truth that we apply as a form of ethics in communication to support service quality is by conveying the actual information without being covered up so that the public also feels satisfied and confident in what we say." (Interview on July 31 2023).

Furthermore, from the results of an interview with the Head of the General Service Section Akmal SE through an interview as follows:

"The principle of truth in communication is through public information disclosure. So in conveying information to the public we are here very open in communicating" (Interview on July 20, 2023).

From the results of the analysis above, it shows that in providing services to the community, Sinjai Regency Government employees have applied the principle of truth in communicating by providing openness and conveying actual information to convince the public of the services provided.

From the results of observations of document data on the principle of truth in providing services to the community can be seen through the following table:

Table 23: Application of the Principle of Truth in Service

Birth Certificate Application Service	
Requirements	1. Photo/Scan of birth certificate, namely from a hospital/Puskesmas/health facility doctor/midwife or birth certificate from the captain of a sea vessel/captain of an airplane, or from the village head/lurah if born at home/other places, including: gardens, rice fields, public forces. 2. Photo/Scan of marriage book/excerpt of marriage certificate/other valid evidence; 3. Photo/Scan of KK where the resident is registered or will be registered as a family member; 4. Police report for children whose origin/existence of their parents is unknown; 5. 5. Residents can make SPTJM for the truth of birth data by filling in F-2.03 and 2 (two) witnesses, if they do not meet the requirements as number 1. 6. Residents can make an SPTJM of the truth as a married couple by filling in F-2.04 and 2 (two) witnesses, if they do not meet the requirements as letter 2. 7.
System, Mechanism and Procedure	1. The applicant comes with the required documents that have been determined; 2. The required documents are received and verified by General Service Officer; 3. The documents are verified again by the Head of General Service Section; 4. Files that have been verified are then inputted into the SIAK; 5. Files that have been inputted into SIAK are signed by the head (in the absence of the head, the file can be signed by another Section Head); 6. The applicant's documents are stamped and recorded in the register book; 7. The documents are handed over to the applicant; 8. The applicant is required to fill in the SKM

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2023

The table above illustrates one example of the application of the principle of truth in service in South Sinjai Regency, namely the delivery of correct information to the public regarding service requirements and procedures.

Furthermore, from the results of the interview by the Head of General Subdivision and

Lamain through an interview as follows:

"The form of the principle of truth in communication is that every information we convey to the public can be accounted for. So the information provided is not perfunctory but is in accordance with the actual facts" (Interview on July 20, 2023).

Furthermore, from the results of an interview with one of the citizens in the Sinjai Regency Government, Mr. Alimuddin explained as follows:

"Regarding the principle of truth in communication, in my opinion, it is also quite good. This means that employees certainly will not lie to their people so that everything that is conveyed to the public should be true" (Interview on July 20, 2023).

The principle of truth is basically a principle that is embraced by a person as a form of morality in himself, so that in carrying out communication he always upholds the values of truth.

Furthermore, from the results of an interview with Mrs. Ramlah said that:

"If the problem of truth depends on what is conveyed, meaning that we as a community must believe in what employees convey to the community because of course they understand better" (Interview on July 20, 2023).

Meanwhile, from the results of an interview with Mrs. Nurliah also said that:

"Yes, what is conveyed to the community is correct, because as a community, of course we really expect accurate information, especially service problems" (Interview on July 18, 2023).

Based on the results and description above, it can be concluded that the indicators of the principle of truth applied in the Office of the Regional Secretary of Kab. Sinjai as a form of organizational communication ethics in supporting service quality as a whole have been carried out well because the Government of Sinjai Regency Government always conveys information disclosure to the public by conveying actual information in accordance with the principles of truth.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that organizational communication ethics in supporting service quality at the Sinjai Regency Government Office as a whole has been implemented well. The principle of kindness in conveying information and when communicating is very good. As for other principles such as the principle of justice, it has also been applied well. The principle of freedom as a whole has been carried out well because the Sinjai Regency Government provides freedom for every community to exercise their rights in expressing opinions. For the principle of truth as a whole has also been carried out well because the Sinjai District Government Government always conveys information disclosure to the public by conveying actual information in accordance with the principle of truth.

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